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Review Article

**ADVANCES IN MANAGING ANEMIA IN ELDERLY IN
PRIMARY CARE**

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Introduction: Anemia is considered to be important risk factors that lead to the development of several late complications and morbidities especially in the elderly. It is associated with higher rates of hospital admissions worse survival outcomes. Most studies have concluded that the risk of anemia continues to increase after an individual passes fifty years of age, with a prevalence of more than twenty percent in individuals older than eighty-five years. it is important to establish the best ways to approach anemic elderly patients and to determine best work-up methods. **Aim of work:** In this review, we will discuss the most recent approaches for management of anemia in the elderly, with a focus on transfusion therapy. **Methodology:** We did a systematic search for anemia in elderly in the emergency department using PubMed search engine (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) and Google Scholar search engine (<https://scholar.google.com>). We only included full articles. **Conclusions:** Anemia is considered to be one of the most common conditions present in the elderly population. anemia can range from mild, to moderate, or even severe in some cases. Most cases off anemia can be asymptomatic and detected accidentally prior to surgeries or on routine investigations. we discussed indications for blood transfusion in anemic elderly patients. Further studies are still required to determine the thresholds for blood transfusion in each subgroup of patients.

Key words: Anemia, elderly, management, recent advances**Corresponding author:**

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INTRODUCTION:

Anemia is considered to be important risk factors that lead to the development of several late complications and morbidities especially in the elderly. It is associated with higher rates of hospital admissions worse survival outcomes [1,2], the elderly population is an important population that needs special medical care. The number of elderly individuals has been recently increasing with a subsequent increase in the prevalence of anemia among this population [3]. In a large study that was based on two databases, up to 10% of individuals older than 65 years, having anemia that meets the criteria of the WHO (having hemoglobin levels that are less than 12 g/dl in females and less than 13 g/dl in males).

Most studies have concluded that the risk of anemia continues to increase after an individual passes fifty years of age, with a prevalence of more than twenty percent in individuals older than eighty-five years [4]. According to recent large studies that included about four thousand elderly individuals with normal baseline hemoglobin levels and followed them for more than fifteen years, the decline in hemoglobin levels (even without qualifying for an anemia diagnosis) led to a significant increased risk of different complications including cognitive impairments [5].

Based on all of this, it is important to recognize and address anemia in all individuals especially the elderly. Therefore, there have been many published guidelines to guide physicians to detect, assess, and manage anemia in different types of patients [6]. However, when it comes to dealing with elderly individuals, it is more difficult to detect anemia risk factors and prevent them, and to manage anemia, due to the presence of several present comorbidities.

Therefore, it is important to establish the best ways to approach anemic elderly patients and to determine best work-up methods, as this is considered an important health-care issue [7]. In this review, we summarize the most recent approaches for management of anemia in the elderly, with a focus on transfusion therapy.

METHODOLOGY:

We did a systematic search for anemia in elderly in the emergency department using PubMed search engine (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) and Google Scholar search engine (<https://scholar.google.com>). We only included full articles.

The terms used in the search were: Anemia, elderly, management, recent advances.

CHARACTERIZATION OF ANEMIA IN THE ELDERLY

During the NHANES study, investigators evaluated more than five thousand elderly individuals, of which, about five hundred individuals fit the WHO criteria for being anemic. Most of included anemic individuals had a mild anemia with hemoglobin levels higher than 10 g/dl. However, they were able to conclude that despite having mild anemia, these individuals were susceptible to the development of severe long term complications including more falls and pathological fractures, less physical activity, impaired cognition, higher rates of dementia, higher hospital admission rates, and worse overall survival [8,9].

In addition to determining the associated long-term complications that followed anemia, authors of the NHANES study also tried to detect associated abnormalities that could have led to the development of anemia. They found that about 35% of included anemic individuals had nutritional problems, mainly iron deficiency. In addition, about 35% of patients had renal disease or a chronic inflammatory disorder. In about 30% of the patients, the cause of the anemia was unknown and no possible explanations were discovered.

These results led to an increase focus on what is now called 'unexplained anemia of the elderly' (UAE), which is, as the name implies, the development of a normocytic anemic status in an elderly individual, with the absence of iron (or other nutritional) deficiencies, renal disease, and inflammatory disorders. These cases are generally characterized by a blunter response to erythropoietin, and are thought to be a result of decreased proliferation. Another study on elderly anemic patients, more than 35% were diagnosed to have unexplained anemia of the elderly [10].

Patients with unexplained anemia of the elderly' are usually found to have low C-RP levels when compared to non-anemic individuals. In addition, these patients have been found to have normal hepcidin levels, which can be used to distinguish them from other causes of anemia where hepcidin can reflect the etiology of the disease. In fact, patients with anemia due to iron deficiency usually have low levels of hepcidin, while patients with anemia of chronic diseases usually have high levels of hepcidin.

¹¹The reason behind the presence of normal hepcidin

levels in patients with unexplained anemia of the elderly' is still not well understood and requires further studies. Some studies are currently conducted to study the role of testosterone deficiency in developing anemia in elderly males.

Apart from unexplained anemia of the elderly, most other cases of anemia in elderly patients have a clear underlying cause. Knowing the exact cause is useful to help treat the anemia. Many etiologies are known to cause anemia, and these include chronic inflammatory disorders, deficiency of iron or other nutritional components, and myelodysplastic diseases. Therefore, following the detection of anemia in an elderly individual, it is important to perform further work up to detect the exact cause of anemia [12].

A previous study included about 232 individuals older than 65 years with a median age of 81 years and found that about 24% of included individuals had the criteria of anemia [13], about 17% of these anemic patients, underwent extensive work up with failure to reveal the underlying etiology of their anemia.¹³ The frequency for each type of anemia among the elderly can vary between studies and changes among different populations. Generally, unexplained anemia of the elderly is present in about 34% to 44% of anemic elderly patients, iron deficiency anemia is present in about 12% to 25% of anemic elderly patients, chronic kidney disease is present in about 4% to 8% of anemic elderly patients, myelodysplastic dysplastic disease is present in about 9% to 16% of anemic elderly patients, hematological malignancy is present in about 2% of anemic elderly patients, and chronic inflammation is present in about 6% to 20% of anemic elderly patients. It is interesting that anemia due the deficiency of folic acid has been significantly decreasing, and in fact, it is not present any more in many developed countries like the United States. The most likely explanation for this is flour fortification. The presence of an underlying cobalamin (vitamin B12) deficiency has been found in about 10% to 20% of anemic elderly patients [8]. However, this deficiency is clinically insignificant in most cases, and most cases have another etiology causing the anemia. The presence of a clinically significant vitamin B12 deficiency causing macrocytic anemia in an elderly patient has been found by multiple studies to be very rare [14].

Based on the results of multiple studies, deficiency of iron has been found by many studies to be the most common cause leading to anemia in elderly patients. The cause of iron deficiency anemia could be a

deficiency in nutrition or chronic minimal blood loss. The later is considered to be more common in developed countries, where the nutritional deficiency of iron is relatively rare. It is important to determine the exact cause of anemia, and the presence of blood loss, as this could be caused by serious conditions like colorectal cancer. 30-33 In addition, diagnosing iron deficiency anemia and determining its cause can be challenging in this age group.

Some studies have found that the levels of IL-6 become higher as the individuals age, which can be associated with anemia development in the elderly population. 23 More recent studies found that IL-6 levels are more likely to increase in anemic elderly patients who have another chronic comorbidity.¹⁰

EVALUATION OF ANEMIA

In many cases, anemia in an elderly patient is asymptomatic and is accidentally discovered when the patient is scheduled to undergo a surgical operation. In fact, anemia is generally common in surgical patients and the degree of anemia is correlated with higher mortality rates during and after the surgery [15]. Therefore, when anemia is discovered in a patient prior to the surgery, it must be taken seriously and treated. In severe cases, rescheduling the surgery may be needed to assess and treat the anemia, and prevent mortality.

MANAGEMENT OF ANEMIA

Management and treatment of anemia differs according to the degree of anemia and the underlying etiology. Therefore, thorough assessment and evaluation must be performed before initiating treatment for an anemic patient. In many cases, the underlying cause must be directly targeted in order to correct the anemia. These include folic acid deficiency, alcoholism, and cobalamin deficiency [16].

The presence of an iron deficiency anemia can be confirmed or excluded following the results of an intravenous trial of iron therapy [17]. This practice is superior to other investigations used to detect iron deficiency, as other investigations may not lead to accurate results in the elderly [18].

The use of erythropoiesis stimulating agents is sometimes indicated for the treatment of anemia in elderly patients. Cases where erythropoiesis stimulating agents can be beneficial include the presence of a chronic kidney disease, a chronic inflammation, patients scheduled for surgery, and

patients with moderate/severe anemia due to myelodysplastic disease [19].

BLOOD TRANSFUSION THERAPY:

Generally, mild-to-moderate anemia is associated with few clinical manifestations. The reason behind this is that the body has mechanisms for compensations that maintain sufficient transport of oxygen. This compensation occurs by higher blood flow, reduced viscosity of blood, higher unloading of oxygen within tissues, elevated bisphosphoglycerate, higher volume of plasma, and altered distribution of blood flow. When levels of hemoglobin become less than 65% of the normal hemoglobin levels (which corresponds to less than 9 or 10 g/dl) more severe clinical manifestations will start to appear. This starts by an increase in the baseline cardiac output that leads to the development of fatigue, shortness of breath, and increased heart rate [20]. Elderly patients who have a history of cardiovascular diseases usually have impaired mechanisms for compensation, and thus may show clinical manifestations earlier in the course of the disease [20].

Complications that follow blood transfusion have led many physicians to attempt other treatment approaches before attempting blood transfusion. Infections are considered among the most common complications that follow blood transfusion. These infections could be with hepatitis C or HIV. Therefore, in patients who are stable and have no apparent risk factors, the use of blood transfusions is not preferred [21]. This practice has been found to be safer than previous practice that indicated blood transfusions until the patients have hemoglobin levels higher than 10 g/dL.

Some protocols recommend the use of transfusions in the treatment of anemia in elderly patients with known cardiovascular diseases, and especially when they are scheduled for surgery. This is because anemic cardiovascular patients are known to have higher mortality rates than non-cardiovascular patients [22].

A previous study included about two thousand patients who underwent surgeries and refused to receive any blood transfusion. Among these patients, mortality rate was 3.2% and anemia was found in 28% of them before the surgery. Investigators found that about 16% of deaths occurred within 1 day following the surgery, while about 40% of deaths occurred in the first week. Cardiovascular-patients had mortality rates that were 4.3 times higher than

non-cardiovascular patient. Results of this study emphasize that the presence of cardiovascular diseases decreases the patients' tolerability to anemia and low levels of hemoglobin.²³

Acute Coronary Syndromes (ACS)

The presence of acute coronary syndrome in a patient who is scheduled to undergo surgery is associated with higher rates of anemia [24]. A previous large retrospective cohort was conducted in the United States on more than 79 thousand elderly patients who had a history of prior hospital admission for myocardial infarction. They found that blood transfusion leads to significant improvements in survival when administrated in patients who had hematocrit less than 33% [25].

The use of blood transfusion in patients with acute coronary syndrome remains to be an area of debate with varying results. In a study that included more than twenty-four thousand patients in twenty-seven countries, authors were able to conclude that there is a significant correlation between the presence of acute coronary syndrome and reduced rates of blood transfusion. In another US study of fort-four thousand anemic patients with acute coronary syndrome, about 10% of patients received transfusions due to having hematocrit levels lower than 24%. These transfusions led to significant improvement in overall survival of these patients. On the other hand, they found that when anemic patients with hematocrit levels higher than 24% received blood transfusion, this was not associated with significant changes in survival and mortality rates. A recent systematic review of ten observational studies on blood transfusion in anemic patients with a history of myocardial infarction showed, however, that blood transfusion was associated with worse overall survival outcomes [26].

In a small clinical trial that included forty-five patients with myocardial infarctions, and hematocrit less than 30%, investigators randomized the patients into receiving blood transfusions to keep hematocrit higher than 30%, or receiving blood transfusion to keep hematocrit levels higher than 24% They measured mortality rates, the recurrence of myocardial infarction attacks, and the development of congestive heart failure. They found that the second group that did only receive transfusions to maintain hematocrit higher than 24% was associated with better outcomes, and the other group had worse outcomes.

The hemoglobin (or hematocrit) thresholds below

which blood transfusion must be started remains to be controversial issue. This becomes a more challenging issue in patients who have comorbidities and risk factors like coronary artery disease or cerebrovascular events.²⁷

In the TRACS trial, patients were randomized to receive blood transfusion to either maintain hematocrit higher than 24% or maintain hematocrit higher than 30% following undergoing surgical operations [28]. Investigators concluded that 30-day overall survival rates did not significantly differ between the two groups. The FOCUS study, on the other hand, included anemic elderly patients with high-risk of developing cardiovascular complications, and who underwent an operation for hip fracture repair. They found that patients with hemoglobin of 8 g/dL or higher were able to tolerate the surgery without the need for blood transfusion [29].

It is important to realize that there are major limitations in most these mentioned prospective trials. In most these trials, eligible patients who are willing and consent to participate in the trial may not reflect all patients with different characteristics in clinical practice. Therefore, results of these trials could not be accurately generalized on the general elderly population [30]. In fact, a major concern on these trials is present which the possible presence of selection bias is.

Clinical Practice Guidelines

In this section of the manuscript, we will summarize currently applied guidelines for the use of blood transfusion for anemia management and treatment. Most published guidelines recommend the consideration of patients' characteristics like age along with the presence of other comorbidities before making a decision of transfusing blood. All guidelines recommend against blood transfusion therapy in any individual with hemoglobin that is higher than 10 g/dL regardless of other factors. On the other hand, all guidelines recommend for the use of blood transfusion therapy in patients with hemoglobin that is less than 6 g/dL, also regardless of other factors [31].

CONCLUSIONS:

Anemia is considered to be one of the most common conditions present in the elderly population. anemia can range from mild, to moderate, or even severe in some cases. Most cases off anemia can be asymptomatic and detected accidentally prior to surgeries or on routine investigations. However, anemia among the elderly population is known to be

associated with severe late complications along with decreased overall survival rates. Moreover, patients with anemia have significantly higher risk of developing post-operative complications and higher post-operative mortality rates. Therefore, proper assessment and treatment of anemia is essential when dealing with older patients. Causes of anemia in the elderly can be nutritional deficiencies, chronic inflammatory disease, or idiopathic. Other causes are generally less common. Most case of anemia are treated by targeting the underlying etiology. In some cases, blood transfusion is indicated. Blood transfusion, however, is associated with multiple complications and adverse events, making it no preferred to use unless necessary. In this paper, we discussed indications for blood transfusion in anemic elderly patients. Further studies are still required to determine the thresholds for blood transfusion in each subgroup of patients.

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